

Antibody Characterization Report for Rab27A

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

Author(s): Vera Ruíz Moleón¹, Riham Ayoubi¹, Peter S. McPherson¹ and Carl Laflamme^{1*}

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Target:

Recommended protein name: Rab27A

Alternative protein name: Ras-related protein Rab-27A

Gene name: *RAB27A*

Uniprot: P51159

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized eleven Rab27A commercial antibodies for Western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. An HAP1 *RAB27A* KO line is available at Horizon discovery and was used in this study. Expression of Rab27A protein in HAP1 is adequate as determined through DepMap [3, 4].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC001240c001	CVCL_TI06	HAP1	<i>RAB27A</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Rab27A antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Abclonal	A23993**	6100003559	AB_3083442	recombinant-mono	ARC61834	rabbit	1.91	Wb,IF
Bio-Techne	AF7245	CFVM0120121	AB_10973494	polyclonal	-	sheep	0.20	Wb
Bio-Techne	MAB7245**	CMPX0119121	AB_3075307	recombinant-mono	2537A	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	69295**	2	AB_2799759	recombinant-mono	D7Z9Q	rabbit	0.08	Wb,IP,IF
Cell Signaling Technology	95394**	10180028	AB_2800247	recombinant-mono	D7V6B	rabbit	0.01	Wb,IP,IF
Proteintech	16868-1-AP	9045	AB_2176716	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.13	Wb
Proteintech	17817-1-AP	48869	AB_2176728	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.33	Wb,IP,IF
Synaptic Systems	168 013	08-Jan	AB_887766	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb,IP
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA1-172*	RD232787	AB_2608617	monoclonal	4D3F11	mouse	1.00	WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-102522	YA3806213A	AB_2851924	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-79904	YA3806947A	AB_2747019	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb,IF

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the Rab27A antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Or: Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-sheep antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A16041). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21429 and A21424). Alexa-555-conjugated donkey anti-sheep secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A-21436).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent cat. number 609-065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Antibody screening by Western blot

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. HAP1 WT and *RAB27A* KO (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and Western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual Western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk

for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg or 20 µl of antibody 69295** and 10 µl of antibody 95394** to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse and sheep antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and Western blot precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. Prot-A:HRP (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8651) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 2.0 µg/ml.

Figure 1: Rab27A antibody screening by Western blot

Figure 2: Rab27A antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 1: Rab27A antibody screening by Western blot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and *RAB27A* KO were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for Western blot with the indicated Rab27A antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: A23993** at 1/1000, AF7245 at 1/200, MAB7245** at 1/200, 69295** at 1/1000, 95394** at 1/200, 16868-1-AP at 1/200, 17817-1-AP at 1/1000, 168 013 at 1/1000, MA1-172* at 1/200, PA5-102522 at 1/200, PA5-79904 at 1/200. Predicted band size: 24.8 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: Rab27A antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated Rab27A antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein. Samples were washed and processed for Western blot with the indicated Rab27A antibody. For Western blot, 95394** was used at 1/200. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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